

COMPUTER-AIDED DETECTION OF COLITIS ON COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY USING A VISUAL CODEBOOK

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ABSTRACT

Colitis is inflammation of the colon that is frequently associated with infection and immune compromise. In this paper, we propose an automatic method for colitis detection in abdominal CT scans. We first used a visual codebook constructed by clustering feature vectors from a set of training image patches to detect the suspicious colitis regions. The initial detections included false detection points located in various organs including muscle, kidney and liver. We reduced the false positives by applying masks of these regions obtained from whole-organ segmentation. We tested our method on a CT dataset with 20 cases of colitis and 15 non-colitis cases. Average detected lesion volume for positive cases is 205ml; for negative cases is 97ml. Sixteen out of the 22 positive cases were correctly identified, yielding a sensitivity of 72.7%; 4 out of 15 negative cases were incorrectly identified, yielding a specificity of 73.3%.

Index Terms— CT, colon, colitis, visual codebook

1. INTRODUCTION

Abdominal computed tomography (CT) can be used to help diagnose many clinically important abnormalities including tumors, infections, injury and inflammation. Colitis is an inflammation of the colon which can have many different causes, including infection, chronic inflammation such as ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease, immunocompromise and lack of blood flow (ischemic colitis). Colitis can be debilitating or life threatening, and early detection is essential to initiate proper treatment [1]. On CT, colitis is often associated with thickening of the colon wall. The oral contrast material trapped between nodular thickened edematous haustral folds separated by mucosal ridges is a classic radiologic sign known as the “accordion” sign [2, 3]. Fig.1 shows an example of a patient with colitis on CT.

In this paper, we propose an automatic method for colitis detection in abdominal CT scans. The visual codebook has proven its effectiveness in object recognition and texture classification [4-6]. We used classifiers with a visual codebook that was trained for classifying colitis vs. different organs and tissues. The suspicious regions of colitis were

first detected by the classifiers. The initial detections included false detections located in muscle, kidney and liver. We reduced the false positives by applying masks of these regions obtained from whole-organ segmentation. With a test dataset contain 20 cases of colitis and 15 non-colitis cases, our method yielded a sensitivity of 72.7% and a specificity of 73.3%.

Fig.1: One example of colitis (marked by red arrows) with colon wall thickening. The oral contrast material trapped between nodular thickened edematous haustral folds separated by mucosal ridges is called the “accordion” sign by radiologists.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The main algorithms for colitis detection consist of two stages: initial detection for suspicious areas using a visual codebook and false detection reduction.

2.1. Visual codebook construction for colitis region

The suspicious colitis areas were detected using the visual codebook framework shown in Fig.2. Given a set of training image patches, feature extraction methods were first used to obtain the image features. Since the colitis regions in our dataset have relatively coarse image textures, the size of the training image patches was selected to be 40×40 pixel grey level patches.

Fig.2: Framework of colitis detection using visual codebook. The left side is the training scheme and the right side is the testing scheme. In the testing scheme, the red bounding box shows a positive colitis region and the yellow bounding box shows a negative region.

Gabor filter banks were used to extract features of the training sample, where an image was characterized by its response to a set of orientation and spatial-frequency selective Gabor filters [7, 8]. A Gabor filter $G(x, y, \theta, \phi)$ is obtained by modulating a complex sinusoid with a Gaussian:

$$G(x, y, \theta, \phi) = g(x, y) \cdot \cos(2\pi\theta(x \cos \phi + y \sin \phi)) + ig(x, y) \cdot \sin(2\pi\theta(x \cos \phi + y \sin \phi)), \quad (1)$$

where θ denotes the frequency and ϕ denotes the orientation of the Gabor function. $g(x, y)$ is an isotropic Gaussian function: $g(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} \exp(-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2\sigma^2})$. The response of Gabor filter to an image can be acquired by 2D convolution:

$$R(x, y, \theta, \phi) = \iint I(p, q)G(x - p, y - q, \theta, \phi) dp dq, \quad (2)$$

where $I(x, y)$ denotes the image, and $R(x, y, \theta, \phi)$ denotes the filtering response with frequency θ and orientation ϕ . The Gabor filter banks were designed with 5 scales and 8 orientations, meaning each pixel can generate a 40 (5×8) dimensional vector by Gabor filtering and concatenation. The codebook was created by quantizing the feature vector using a vector quantization algorithm, e.g., k-means in our experiment. There were 64 cluster centers (codewords) in the codebook. Histogram representation was used to

describe the training samples. Each codeword represents one bin in the histogram. By mapping the feature vectors that are closest to the codeword to the corresponding bins, we obtained a histogram to represent the image patch with frequent variations of codewords.

The testing was run on the CT slices. We sampled the image every 10 pixels and selected the 40×40 patch around each sampled pixel for testing. The test samples went through the same feature extraction process as the training samples by performing 2D convolution with Gabor filter banks. The feature vectors were then represented by a histogram of codewords which were built by the training scheme. The image quantization results were then sent into a classifier which was trained by the codebook. We used support vector machines (SVM) for classification.

2.2. False detection reduction

The initial detection using the above method yielded many false positives within various organs, including muscle, kidney and liver, as shown in Fig.3(a).

Since colon segmentation on non-CTC data is not practical, to reduce the false detections, we used a binary mask that contained the segmented regions of these organs. The algorithms for organ segmentation followed our in-house technique [9-11].

For muscle segmentation, 1) atlas-based models were initialized with prior knowledge at multiple key positions since the appearance and shape of the muscle change greatly along the body from thorax to pelvis; 2) starting from the most superiorly-located slice, the atlas model was refined using active contours, where spatial relationships between muscle and pre-segmented other organs such as rib, spine, subcutaneous fat, and visceral fat, was used as external force of the active contours. Muscle within the refined atlas model was segmented using thresholding of image intensity; 3) the atlas model of next slice was initialized using the context information, i.e. the refined or pre-defined atlas models of adjacent slices. Then the algorithm cycled back to step 2 until the most inferior slice was reached.

The liver region was obtained by our in-house liver segmentation method [8]. Fig.3(b) shows the remaining intra-abdominal region after the muscle segmentation. For kidney segmentation, we 1) localized kidney search regions by exploiting the segmented liver and spleen and body symmetry; 2) used a probabilistic shape prior to handle the situations where the kidney touches other organs; and 3) employed efficient belief propagation on the shape prior to extract the kidneys. Fig.3(c) shows the kidney segmentation results.

2.3. Measurement

We measured the 3D volume of the lesion region based on the convex region formed by a group of detection points. The detection points were grouped based on connected

component labeling in 3D space. The volume of the lesion region in 2D slice was calculated as the product of the area of the region and the slice thickness.

The lesion volume is used to decide whether the case is positive. A Bayesian decision rule for minimum error rate classification was used to obtain the threshold of lesion volume.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. Dataset

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.3: (a) Initial detection results with false detection points located in various organs (blue: correct detection on colitis region; red: false detection on muscle; green: false detection on kidney; yellow: remaining false detections). (b) The remaining intra-abdominal region after muscle segmentation. (c) Kidney segmentation results.

(a)

(b)

Fig.4: Examples of training image patches from the dataset. (a) Positive patches from colitis regions. (b) Negative patches came from regions of various organs, including

liver, muscle, kidney, bone, vessels, normal colon and small bowel.

Experiments were carried out on a dataset of 37 contrast-enhanced CT scans, with pixel size ranging from 0.57 to 0.97 mm. There were 11 cases with slice thickness 5mm and 26 cases with slice thickness 1mm. Of the 37 cases, 22 were positive for colitis and 15 were negative. For each case, we manually selected 100 image patches as candidates for training. Positive patches were from colitis regions. Negative patches came from the regions of various organs including liver, muscle, kidney, bone, vessels, normal colon and small bowel. Fig.4 shows examples of training image positive and negative patches.

Two fold cross validation was used for training and testing. The dataset was separated into 2 groups with non-overlapping cases, with one group for training and one group for testing. Then the training and testing set were reversed. During the training process, the codebook was trained by randomly selecting 2000 image patches with 1000 positive and negative patches in each.

3.3. Results

The ROC curve of the experimental results is shown in Fig.5, with an AUC of 0.75. Average detected lesion volume for positive cases is 205ml; for negative cases is 97ml. Sixteen out of the 22 positive cases were correctly identified, yielding a sensitivity of 72.7% (16/22); 4 out of 15 negative case were identified as positive, yielding a specificity of 73.3% (11/15).

Fig.6 presents the detection results on positive and negative examples.

Fig.5: ROC curve of the experimental results shows the sensitivity against false positive.

4. DISCUSSION

Due to the complexity of the abdominal region on CT, for example the tortuous course of the colon which varies greatly in length and position amongst different patients and even on serial scans of the same patient, and the variable contents and distension of the colon [12,13], detecting colitis regions is a difficult task. The proposed method can pick up most of the colitis regions successfully. The detections on

the positive images shown in Fig.6 are much larger than those on the negative images, providing a means of distinguishing true from false positive detections. Our method may also pick up regions of small bowel thickening, in which the small bowel can be subtracted by our in house technique for small bowel segmentation [14]. False positives often happened in the clutter of the image. A more comprehensive feature extraction and classification method may prevent them. False negatives happened in the cases that the “accordion” sign was not clear enough for the algorithms to detect, or the lesion region was clear but too small and eliminated by the decision rules.

5. CONCLUSION

We proposed a novel method that can accurately detect colitis on contrast-enhanced CT scans using a visual codebook. Our method may have potential for improving the diagnostic efficacy of CT for detecting colon wall thickening and inflammation.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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7. REFERENCES

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Fig.6: Detection results for colitis (marked by red arrows) using the proposed method. Images on the left are the original CT images; images on the right show detections in blue. (a) positive images and (b) negative for colitis.